

Quality Evaluation Systematic Tool

QUEST Checklist: For Qualitative, Quantitative & Mixed Methods Research

Reviewer Name:	
Paper Title:	
Author:	
DOI:	

Appraisal Date:	
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Checklist Section	Question to evaluate	Full description
1. Conceptual Framework	1. Did the study provide an adequate conceptual framework?	1.1 Adequacy of the Conceptual Framework: Assess if concepts are clearly defined, if theories/models are referenced, and if the framework aligns with research questions.
2. Research Questions and Objectives	2. Is the research question clearly defined?	2.1 Clarity of Research Question: Determine if the research question is explicitly stated or implicitly clear.
	3. Was there a clear statement of the aims of the research?	2.2 Statement of Research Aims: Verify if the research goal is clearly stated, the importance of the research is explained, and its relevance to the field or society is addressed.
3. Methods	4. Was the study design appropriate for the stated aim (s)?	3.1 Appropriateness of Study Design: Evaluate if the chosen design aligns with the research questions and objectives.
	5. Was the target/reference population clearly defined? (It is clear who the research was about?)	3.2 Definition of Target Population: Ensure that the target population is explicitly described, including inclusion/exclusion criteria and relevant demographic characteristics.
	6. Was the sample size justified?	3.3 Justification of Sample Size: Confirm that the study explains the rationale for the sample size.
	7. Was a systematic method applied for the selection of the units of analysis that would compose the final sample?	3.4 Systematic Selection of Units of Analysis and Data Collection: Assess if the selection process for units of analysis is systematic, justified, and transparent. Ensure data collection methods are clearly described, including justification for the methods chosen, details on how data were collected (e.g., focus group, semi-structured interviews), and information on any modifications made during the study.
	8. Was a rigorous description of the analysis techniques used carried out?	3.5 Analytical Techniques: Assess if the analysis techniques are clearly described, align with research questions and data type, and justify assumptions for the analysis.
	9. Did the authors take sufficient steps to assure the quality of the study data?	3.6 Quality Assurance of Data: Evaluate if the authors took sufficient steps to ensure the quality of study data, such as using validated and reliable instruments and

		detailing procedures for data cleaning and validation.
4. Results	10. Is it provided a clear and complete description of the relevant demographic and baseline characteristics of the participants?	4.1 Descriptive Data: Provide participant demographics and relevant baseline characteristics.
	11. Is there a clear statement of findings?	4.2 Findings and Main Results: Summarize key findings, explicitly discuss evidence for and against arguments, and discuss the credibility of the findings.
	12. Does the study clearly present the results of subgroup and sensitivity analyses?	4.4 Subgroup and Sensitivity Analyses: Present the results of subgroup and sensitivity analyses, if applicable.
5. Discussion	13. Are the key findings identified and described?	5.1 Key Findings: Summarize key findings in relation to the research objectives.
	14. Are possible similarities or discrepancies with existing literature identified and explained?	5.2 Interpretation of Results: Discuss findings in the context of existing literature and theoretical frameworks.
	15. Are all study limitations and strengths clearly identified?	5.3 Study Strengths and Limitations: Address the strengths and limitations of the study, including sources of bias and generalizability.
	16. How valuable is the discussion?	5.4 Value and Implications of the Discussion: Discuss how the study contributes to existing knowledge, identifies areas for future research, and considers implications for practice and policy.
	17. Are the findings adding value to the available evidence?	5.5 Generalizability and Applicability: Assess the real-world impact, practical implications, and potential for applying the findings in different contexts, including local settings.
6. Additional Information	18. Is it stated whether or not there is a potential conflict of interest or conflicting role of the funders?	6.1 Conflicts of Interest: Declare any conflicts of interest for all authors.
	19. Are ethical considerations explicitly described in the article?	6.2 Ethical Considerations: Confirm ethical approval and adherence to ethical standards for research involving human or animal subjects.
	20. Is data available for replication?	6.3 Data Availability: State the availability of data used in the study (e.g., data is available upon request, publicly accessible, or specify the repository where it can be found).

APPRAISAL SUMMARY: List key points from your critical appraisal that need to be considered when assessing the validity of the results and their usefulness in decision-making.

Item	Positive/Methodologically sound	Negative/Relatively poor methodology	Unknowns
Q1			
Q2			
Q3			
Q4			
Q5			
Q6			
Q7			
Q8			
Q9			
Q10			
Q11			
Q12			
Q13			
Q14			
Q15			
Q16			
Q17			
Q18			
Q19			
Q20			

Instructions

To incorporate the table into the set of selected articles, each question must be assessed and answered with 'yes,' 'no,' or 'not applicable.' This process ensures consistency and accuracy in the classification of the articles. In the following section, each question will

be explained in detail, providing the necessary criteria and context to facilitate a precise and informed response.

Conceptual Framework

1. Did the study provide an adequate conceptual framework?

A conceptual framework connects key concepts and premises, grounding the study within a broader theoretical context (Varpio et al., 2020). An adequate framework should clearly define the fundamental concepts of the research, and establish logical relationships between them and the study's objectives. By incorporating relevant theories, the framework provides structure, ensures coherence, and enhances the study's validity. Without a well-defined conceptual framework, the research may lack clarity, making it difficult to interpret findings in a meaningful way. Therefore, it is essential that the study presents a robust and well-structured conceptual framework aligned with its research question.

Research Questions and Objectives

2. Is the research question clearly defined?

The research question of the study plays a fundamental role in the research process, as it is the first step in guiding the research. It is decisive for making decisions about the design and methods to be followed in order to adequately answer the research question (Bryman, 2007). A well-formulated research question ensures coherence between the research objective, the chosen methodology, and the expected findings, allowing for a structured and systematic approach to answering it. Additionally, a clear and precise research question helps define the theoretical framework, justify the relevance of the study, and contribute to the broader academic discourse on the topic.

3. Was there a clear statement of the aims of the research?

The aims of a study define its overall purpose and should be closely related to the research question (Doody & Bailey, 2016). Clearly stating the goals and objectives of the research is essential, as it provides guidance, ensures consistency, and highlights the relevance of the study to the target population or society. Well-defined objectives help establish a structured approach to data collection and analysis, which facilitates the interpretation of findings. If research objectives are unclear or poorly articulated, it is difficult to assess the validity of the study and effectively answer subsequent research questions. Therefore, a transparent and concise statement of objectives is critical to a well-structured research study (Downes et al., 2016).

Methods

4. Was the study design appropriate for the stated aim(s)?

This question assesses whether the research design was properly aligned with the stated objectives. A well-designed study should provide a methodological framework that allows the research questions to be adequately answered, ensuring the validity and reliability of the findings. The choice of research design (qualitative, quantitative or mixed) should be informed by the nature of the study problem and the research objectives. The authors point out that a well-chosen design enables data collection and analysis in a manner consistent with the theoretical and methodological perspective adopted (Doody & Bailey, 2016). Furthermore, it is essential that the design is explicitly justified in the study, detailing why a specific approach was chosen and how it contributes to valid and reliable results. An inappropriate choice of design may compromise the study's ability to effectively answer its research questions.

5. Was the target/reference population clearly defined? (It is clear who the research was about?)

This question seeks to determine whether the study clearly and precisely specified the population to which the research refers. A proper definition of the target population is essential to ensure the external validity of the study and the applicability of its results. In social research, the target population must be clearly delimited, establishing inclusion and exclusion criteria that define who is part of the study and who is not. In addition, relevant demographic characteristics such as age, gender, socio-economic status, geographic location or other factors relevant to the research context should be specified (Babbie, 2020). A study that does not explicitly define its target population may generate ambiguous results and limit its applicability to other contexts. Therefore, a detailed description of the reference population contributes to the transparency and replicability of the study.

6. Was the sample size justified?

Justifying the sample size is crucial, as it directly impacts the validity, reliability, and generalizability of a study's findings (Lakens, 2022). An insufficient sample size can weaken the statistical power, making it difficult to detect true effects and reducing the credibility of the conclusions. Conversely, an excessively large sample may lead to unnecessary resource consumption without proportional benefits. A well-justified sample size ensures that the data collected align with the study's inferential goals and that the chosen methods for determining the sample size are transparent and appropriate. By clearly outlining the rationale behind the sample size, researchers enhance the robustness of their study and reinforce the validity of their conclusions. In qualitative research, the justification of sample size follows different principles: rather than aiming for representativeness, qualitative studies prioritize depth, richness, and theoretical saturation. In this context, a justified sample size is one that allows for a comprehensive exploration of the research phenomenon and is aligned with the methodological approach adopted (e.g., grounded theory, case study, ethnography). Whether the study is quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-methods, clearly articulating the rationale behind the

sample size enhances the overall robustness of the research and reinforces the validity of its conclusions.

7. Was a systematic method applied for the selection of the units of analysis that would compose the final sample?

This question aims to assess whether the selection of the cases studied was carried out following a rigorous and justified methodology. The selection of the units of analysis in qualitative studies should be based on explicit and systematic criteria to guarantee the validity of the findings (Miles et al., 2013). According to the authors, cases should be chosen strategically, taking into account their relevance to the research and their ability to provide rich and varied information. In addition, the sampling process should be transparent, detailing the criteria used and justifying their relevance to the objectives of the study. The authors suggest that the selection can be based on different approaches, such as purposive sampling, which allows the inclusion of cases with specific characteristics that enrich the understanding of the phenomenon studied. The application of a systematic method in this phase not only reinforces the credibility of the study, but also facilitates replicability and comparability with other research.

8. Was a rigorous description of the analysis techniques used carried out?

The analysis of the methods should provide adequate justification to help ensure the validity and reliability of your study. An adequate description should explain the processes in detail, demonstrate how the processes fit the research questions/type of data in question, and support any underlying assumptions (Müller-Staub, 2012). Such assumptions may relate to the independence of variables, the normality of the data in statistical analysis, or the appropriateness of specific theoretical models for interpreting the results. In qualitative research, it involves explaining coding strategies, thematic analysis, and reliability measures, such as triangulation. Justifying these assumptions from the outset is vital to ensure the reliability of the results and to avoid biases in interpretation. Transparency in methodological approaches allows reproducibility and a better understanding and interpretation of the results.

9. Did the authors take sufficient steps to assure the quality of the study data?

Authors should take appropriate measures to ensure data integrity by using validated and reliable data collection instruments, standardized data collection processes, and rigorous data cleaning and validation processes. These measures help to minimize errors and reduce bias, improving the reproducibility of the study (Condon et al., 2022). This includes information on the calibration of measurement tools, the training of data collectors or interviewers in qualitative studies, and the treatment of missing or inconsistent data; when these quality control methods are described, it adds credibility to the research. Without adequate quality control, the reliability of the study's findings may be compromised

Results

10. Is it provided a clear and complete description of the relevant demographic and baseline characteristics of the participants?

A robust and complete description of baseline and demographic characteristics of participants is critical for contextualizing the findings of the study, and for interpretability and reproducibility of the results. Demographic information, including age, gender, socioeconomic status, educational background, and other pertinent descriptors, allows readers to evaluate the generalizability of the sample and to what extent it can be applied to other groups. This highlights the importance of clearly and completely representing each of these variables to establish the validity of a study, enable reproduction of the experiments, and cross-study comparisons (Schulz et al., 2010).

11. Is there a clear statement of findings?

Findings should highlight the main findings in a clear and structured manner, providing sufficient evidence to assess their strength and limitations. They should also be structured logically and in line with the study's objectives, showing the relationship between the data and the research questions, ensuring consistency with the analysis. Tables, graphs or figures should be used strategically to complement the text. Furthermore, it is crucial to balance the description of the data with its interpretation, avoiding extrapolations that correspond to the discussion (Regehr, 2001).

12. Does the study clearly present the results of subgroup and sensitivity analyses?

If applicable by the nature of the study (i.e. clinical trials, observational studies, and meta-analyses) (Rosenbaum, 2005; Thabane et al., 2013), the results of subgroup and sensitivity analyses should be clearly defined to assess the robustness and applicability of the findings (Gil-Sierra et al., 2020). Subgroup analyses may uncover effects that differ depending on factors characterizing populations, while sensitivity analyses provide confidence in the conditions under which results hold across a variety of assumptions and analytical approaches. In qualitative research, although statistical sensitivity analysis is not applicable, researchers can demonstrate robustness through analytical triangulation, reflexivity, or the comparison of alternative interpretations. These alternative analyses allow for a critical examination of how different coding approaches, theoretical lenses, or researcher perspectives might influence the interpretation of data. Clearly reporting these procedures enhances the transparency and credibility of qualitative findings and serves a similar function to sensitivity analyses in quantitative studies.

Discussion

13. Are the key findings identified and described?

Key findings are explained and described to demonstrate how they support the study's objectives. A clear and structured presentation improves comprehension, allows for the evaluation of methodological rigor, and facilitates comparison with previous research. This strengthens the study's contributions and guides future research, ensuring the findings remain relevant in academic discourse.

14. Are possible similarities or discrepancies with existing literature identified and explained?

A quality study should contextualize its findings in the existing literature, highlighting similarities that reinforce their validity and discrepancies that provide new perspectives. Explaining these differences allows us to identify possible methodological limitations, variations in the data or divergent theoretical approaches. This comparison with the literature improves the understanding of the phenomenon studied and contributes to academic debate, guiding future research (Crandall et al., 2001).

15. Are all study limitations and strengths clearly identified?

The limitations of the study are those aspects of the design or methodology that affected or influenced the interpretation of the research findings. These limitations impose constraints on the ability to generalise the results, extend their practical application, or determine their usefulness, whether due to the initial design choices, the method used to ensure internal and external validity, or unforeseen challenges that arose during the course of the study. All research has some limitations so the researcher should be aware of them in their study design. If this is not addressed, the researcher may not have a good understanding of the study as a whole (Downes et al., 2016).

16. How valuable is the discussion?

The Discussion section in a research article is essential, as it is where the researcher interprets and analyses the obtained results, placing them within the context of existing knowledge. This section allows for the evaluation of the validity of the proposed hypothesis, the identification of study limitations, and the suggestion of future research directions. Additionally, it facilitates the comparison of findings with previous studies, enriching scientific debate and contributing to the advancement of knowledge in the field (Annesley, 2010).

17. Are the findings generalizable or applicable to similar contexts?

The results of the study can be extended beyond the specific sample analyzed and applied to other contexts, populations or similar situations. The external validity of the study is assessed, i.e., the extent to which the results can be reproduced or used in different contexts without losing their reliability. Factors such as the size and representativeness of the sample, the research design and the context in which the study was conducted influence the generalizability potential. In practical terms, this helps determine whether the findings have a broader impact or are limited to a specific group or situation. Low generalizability does not necessarily mean that the study is worthless, but it does suggest that its conclusions should be interpreted with caution outside the context analyzed.

Additional Information

18. Is it stated whether or not there is a potential conflict of interest or conflicting role of the funders?

It is crucial that any conflicts of interest or the organisations involved in funding the study are explicitly declared within the text. This disclosure can shed light on the underlying motivations for conducting the research. When a study is funded by a specific organisation, the researcher may, consciously or unconsciously, interpret the findings in a way that aligns with the organisation's ideals; similarly, if the researcher has prior experience in a particular area, their personal views and beliefs may influence the interpretation of the results. It is the responsibility of the reader to identify such potential biases and assess whether these conflicts of interest are significant. These should be clearly stated in the relevant sections of the text.

19. Are ethical considerations explicitly described in the article?

Ethical considerations should be indicated in the article, whether or not there are any. It is important to obtain ethical approval from study participants before conducting research if it has involved animals or humans (Miteu, 2024).

20. Is data available for replication?

The availability of the data should be indicated, i.e., the research should indicate whether the data used in the study are publicly available (anyone can access them) or whether they are restricted data for which a prior request must be made. In both cases, the repository or database where the data can be found must be indicated.

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